

Response of Reproductive Performance Related to Blood Metabolite Concentration in Post-Induction Hormone Pasundan Cows

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Abstract.

Twenty Pasundan cows were used in this study to see the success of multiple method prostaglandin induction and ovulation synchronization using GnRH in scheduled artificial insemination (AI) and the relationship between blood metabolite concentrations to estrous intensity, service preconception and calving rate in Pasundan heifers. The cows were divided into two treatments, 1) simultaneous vigorously with multiple injection of 5 ml dose of PGF2 α , 2) a combination of PGF2 α and GnRH hormones as much as 2.5 ml per head intramuscularly. Cows in heat are artificially inseminated twice with an interval of 6 hours. The variables observed were estrous intensity, service preconception and calving rate, β -hydroxy butyric acid (BHBA), blood urea nitrogen (BUN), and non esterificated acid (NEFA). Data were processed by analysis of variance and correlation regression. The results showed that the pregnancy rate for the combination of prostaglandins and GnRH was better than double injection of prostaglandins (80.0% vs 70.0%)., the average BHBA, NEFA and BUN, respectively 11.75 ± 1.32 mg / dl vs 11.73 ± 1.78 mg / dl, 1.90 ± 0.20 million / μ l, vs 1.8 ± 0.24 , million / μ l, 23.44 ± 2.60 mg / dL vs 22.92 ± 1.53 mg / dL. The results of the regression analysis showed that the concentrations of BHBA, NEFA, and BUN had a significant relationship ($P < 0.05$) to service perception with a determination coefficient of 25.38%, to a conception rate with a determination coefficient of 50.82%. It was concluded that the concentration of β -hydroxybutyric acid (BHBA), non-esterified fatty acid (NEFA), and blood urea nitrogen (BUN), had a strong relationship with the coefficient of determination ($> 50\%$) and was inversely related to the conception rate, but had a weak relationship. with a coefficient of determination ($< 50\%$) and inversely proportional to the service preconception.

Keywords: Pasundan cows, exogenous hormone induction, Reproductive performance, Blood Metabolite.

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is a tropical country that consequently has hot temperatures. This results in a) lack of water availability, b) low quality of feed. Hot and humid temperatures in Indonesia affect the body's metabolism of livestock. Grass in the tropics has high crude fiber, this is also found in agricultural waste given to beef cattle. This causes low feed efficiency in the tropics, which is no less important is the heat temperature with high humidity causes high ectoparasites and endoparasites, both of which also have an impact on reproductive failure both in the emergence of lust to early embryo death, therefore beef cattle which has adaptability in the tropics. Pasundan cattle are local livestock in West Java which have been designated as local Indonesian livestock based on the Decree of the Minister of Agriculture of the Republic of Indonesia Number 1051 / Kpts / RI / SR.10 / 2014. In this case, Pasundan cows have resistance to poor feed, hot temperatures, ectoparasites, and endoparasites as well as high reproductive power but do not have high reproductive efficiency due to poor reproductive management and extensive maintenance systems.

The problem that occurs in Pasundan cattle in the Bogor area is the occurrence of a calving interval of 14-15 months, caused by 1). Calves are weaned at the age of more than four months (> 4 months). 2) The failure of artificial insemination so that the average S / C was 1.6 times, and 3). Mean first time married at the

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age of 2 (two) years (Setiawati et al, 2018) [1]. One of the efforts to increase the reproductive efficiency of Pasundan cattle can be done through the application of heat synchronization technology combined with increasing fertility of cows, as well as the IB technique as technology. With the application of this technology package, it is hoped that it will improve the reproductive performance of Pasundan cows to produce calves so that the calving distance is shorter. Röttgen et al., (2018) [2], states that exogenous injection of prostaglandins (PGF₂ α) is very effective for bullying in heat in dairy cows, Ongole crossbreed beef cattle (Nuryadi et al., 2011) [3], Aceh cows (Hafizuddin et al., 2012) [4], Bali cattle (Handayani et al., 2012) [5], Currently, several methods of synchronization of lust have been developed, including the use of progesterone, prostaglandin and estrogen preparations (Kune and Najamudin, 2002[6]; Bharali et al., 2014[7]; Ma'ruf et al., 2016). [8]. The heat level of cattle will certainly provide a clue for the timing of AI (Bernandi, et al., 2016[9]; Stotzel et al., 2013 [10],

The use of heat manipulation technology followed by the provision of gonadotrophin-releasing hormone (GnRH) can trigger signs of heat and increase the fertility of cows, namely stimulating follicle growth to ovulate, and increasing the number of corpus luteum and placental mass (Bharali, et al., 2014) [7], so that can increase the chances of pregnancy in livestock (Hassan et al., 2016).) [11], GnRH injection can induce ovulation and then stimulate an increase in endogenous FSH, which is followed by a wave of follicles in cows (Putro and Kusumawati, 2014) [12]. For successful estrous synchronization and insemination and to obtain the maximum percentage of pregnancy, cows must have a BCS of 5 or more (for scoring 1-9). This is in line with Nascimento et al., (2014) [13], which stated that the feed factor is very decisive for the success of the estrus synchronization program and IB. Forage or other coarse materials/ is a potential source of energy for ruminants. Abidin et al. (2012) [14], stated that nutrition is indispensable for physiological reproduction in livestock. Lack of nutrition disrupts and the synthesis and regulation of reproductive hormones resulting in a less clear sexual response. About 75% of carbohydrates in ruminant rations come from forage in the form of crude fiber, most of which is about 60 to 75% will be digested in the fermentative digestion process in the rumen. Butyric acid is a component of short-chain fatty acids (SCFA) or organic acids produced by intestinal microbial fermentation of food carbohydrates which are digested both by starch and dietary fiber. Butyric acid causes the pH to decrease which can suppress the growth of gram-negative bacteria, such as coliform bacteria in the digestive tract (Canani et al., 2011) [15],

Metabolic Profile Tests (MPT) are a series of specific blood Elisa tests, which are very useful as an indicator that the body's homeostasis mechanism keeps blood parameters within the physiological range (Gross et al. 2011). [16] This test can be used to check the nutritional and metabolic status of livestock individually or in groups. The blood metabolic profile includes Blood Urea Nitrogen (BUN), β -hydroxybutyric acid (BHBA), Non-esterified fatty acids (NEFA). Unesterified fatty acids, better known as NEFA (non -esterified fatty acids), are the result of overhauling of fat reserves in the form of triacylglycerols and triglycerides in adipose tissue / fat depots, which can produce energy through oxidation in liver and muscle tissue. If livestock lack energy due to insufficient energy intake, the energy reserves in the form of fat will be converted into NEFA and glycerol which can be used as a source of energy for lactating cows (Tasse, 2014). [17], The blood metabolic profile also has great benefits for the early identification of energy metabolism disorders in cattle (Prodanovic et al. 2012) [18]. Low concentrations of blood glucose and total protein lead to impaired reproductive hormone function and not optimal reproductive tract function, leading to failure of the follicle, oocyte, and embryo development which will lead to premature embryonic death and failure of fertilization which results in repeated mating (Khan et al., 2010) [19]. BUN levels illustrate the balance between urea formation and protein catabolism and urea excretion by the kidneys (Pemayun (2002) [20]. Low glucose levels can cause high levels of non -esterified fatty acids (NEFA) and BHBA (β -hydroxybutyric acid) which have a toxic effect on follicles. , oocytes, embryos, and fetuses and decreased GnRH secretion by the hypothalamus (Adewuyil et al., 2005) [21]. High urea concentration in the blood (BUN) suppresses the immune system, lowers uterine pH, decreases the production of prostaglandins, affects the pituitary-pituitary-ovary axis. eggs (National Research Council

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2001[22]; Roy et al. 2011) [23], have toxic effects on sperm, eggs, and embryos and result in decreased reproductive function (Roy et al. 2011[23], and Bindari et al. 2013[24],)

This study was conducted to see the success of multiple method prostaglandin inductions and ovulation synchronization using GnRH in scheduled IB and the relationship between blood metabolite concentrations to estrous intensity, service pre-conception and calving rate in Pasundan heifers.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The research used material in the form of 20 Pasundan cows aged 2.0 - 2.5 years owned by breeders who are members of the Mekar Tani 2 group. having its address at Singasari Village, Jonggol District, Bogor Regency, West Java Province. The selection of the acceptor cattle for the IB was based on the criteria of having a body condition score (BCS = 3, according to the assessment of the BCS 1-5 range (Alapati et al., (2010). [25],) All cattle were palpated rectally to determine their reproductive status and ensure that the cows are not In a pregnant state, the selected animals are healthy, non-pregnant, and have never been pregnant. The selected animals are given an identification number and the required data are recorded, such as the owner of the livestock, age, characteristics of the livestock, and others.

Tools and materials

The tools used include a 10 ml syringe, even jet, Sahli pipette, stirring rod, haemometer, standard glass tube, slide glass, EDTA (Ethylene Diamine Tetraacetic Acid) vacuum tube, microscope, counter, Sahli tube, tube capillary, centrifuge, reader, hemoglobinometer and dropper. as well as KIT BUN, BHBA, and NEFA, gloves, clasps and rope, KIT equipment for artificial insemination and pregnancy examination for cameras, and office stationery. The materials used were prostaglandin hormone preparations (Lutalyse TM, dinoprost tromethamine, Upjohn, Kalamazoo, USA); and gonadotropin realizing hormone, (Fertagyl, Intervet Animal Health UK Ltd, Cambridge), frozen semen from Pasundan cattle produced by the Institute for Artificial Insemination in Lembang. livestock blood and serum. being observed. chemicals to measure the concentration of blood metabolites (KIT, Sigma Chemical Co., St Louis, MO

Research Methods and Design

The research method used was an experimental design based on a nested pattern with a completely randomized basic design. All experimental cows were given

basal feed (forage) and additional feed according to each local environmental condition, while drinking water is given and A total of 20 Pasundan cows were allocated to 2 (two) treatment groups, namely group P1: 10 were injected with prostaglandin (PGF₂ α) at a dose of 5 ml/head 2 (two) times with an interval of 11 days to uniform their physiological conditions. each animal as a control., group P2: 10 were injected with prostaglandin (PGF₂ α) at a dose of 5 ml/head intramuscularly for 2 (two) times with an interval of 11 days, but on day 9 were injected with as much gonadotropin realizing hormone (GnRH) 2.5 ml/bird intramuscularly.

Observed Variables

1. Service per conception is the number of marriages performed until pregnancy or the average number of inseminations required by a female cow until pregnancy occurs in units of times (Iskandar, 2011) [26],
2. Calving rate is the number of Pasundan cows that are pregnant as a result of the first artificial insemination (AI) divided by the number of cows bred times 100 in percent;
3. Concentrations of blood metabolite profiles include β -hydroxybutyric acid (BHBA), Non-esterified fatty acids (NEFA) and Blood Urea Nitrogen (BUN), measured at the time of estrus and 60 days and 150 days of pregnancy examination.

Synchronization Treatment

A total of 20 Pasundan heifers were divided into 2 groups, namely 10 cows synchronized with the double injection of prostaglandins ((Lutalyse TM, Upjohn, Kalamazoo USA, containing 25 mg of Dinoprost Tromethamin), with a dose of 5 ml/head intramuscularly for 2 (two) times with an interval of 11 days, but on the 9th-day gonadotropin releasing hormone was injected (Fertagyl, Intervet Animal Health UK Ltd, Cambridge; which contains 100 µg of Gonadorelin which is synthetic GnRH)), at a dose of 2.5 ml/head intramuscularly. Cows that are in heat are directly on IB 2 times with an interval of 6 hours after the first artificial insemination (AI)

Estrus Observation

Observation of estrus was carried out twice a day, namely in the morning (06.00 - 08.00 and 17.00 - 18.00) three days in a row after the last PGF₂ α injection. The signs of a cow experiencing estrus are indicated by the behavior of the cow, such as a cow that looks restless, often gossiping, and sometimes tries to ride the female next to it. In addition, confirmation was also performed by palpation per rectally to observe uterine tension and the presence of developing follicles.

Pregnancy examination

Cows resulting from IB after 2 months do not show heat again will be done rectal palpation by feeling the uterus to detect uterine enlargement that occurs during pregnancy (Jainudeen and Hafez, 2008) [27],

Blood Collection and Preparation

Blood collection was carried out when the cow was estrus, was pregnant for 60 days and 150 days. Blood serum for measurement of blood metabolite levels was taken from the bovine jugular vein using a 10 ml disposable syringe. The blood drawn is put in a test tube and placed in a flask filled with ice. The blood is then brought into the laboratory for serum and allowed to stand for 30 minutes before doing centrifuge. The centrifuge was carried out at a speed of 2500 rpm for 15 minutes. The serum is then taken from the tube with a micropipette and put in the Diefendorf. Serum was stored in the freezer until used for hormonal analysis. Blood metabolite analysis was performed using enzymatic techniques using a KIT (Sigma Chemical Co., St Louis, MO) with a range of readily available standards.

Blood Metabolite Examination

Analysis of β -hydroxybutyric acid (BHBA), the concentration of BHBA was measured using an enzymatic technique using KIT (Sigma Chemical Co., St Louis, MO) with a range of available standards. BHBA uses Precisian XtraTM Blood Test Strips, one drop of blood each for BHBA analysis, and takes 25 seconds for each sample.

Analysis of Non-Esterified Fatty Acid (NEFA) levels was performed using the Max Discovery NEFA Assay Kit (Sigma Chemical Co., St Louis, MO). The wavelength used is 550 nm for the sample or standard used.

Analysis of Blood Urea Nitrogen (BUN) was measured using an enzymatic technique using a KIT (Sigma Chemical Co., St Louis, MO) with a standard range that is readily available. These parameters were analyzed using the Auto analyzer (Refloton (R) plus). The method is to put one drop of blood (30µl) on the rod of the kit. Each parameter uses a different rod kit, then enter it into the Auto analyzer, wait a few minutes, the tool will read the results automatically

Data analysis

The data obtained, such as estrous intensity scores and pregnant cattle, were statistically analyzed for differences between estrous synchronization treatments, using the Chi-square test (Steel and Torrie, 1993). To

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determine the shape and closeness of the relationship between the dependent variable of service preconception and conception rate (Y) and the independent variable of blood metabolite concentration (X), a correlation regression analysis was performed using Microsoft Excel ®2010. SPSS.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Blood Metabolite Concentration Profile

Metabolic Profile Tests (MPT) are a series of specific blood analysis tests, which are very useful as an indicator that the body's homeostasis mechanism keeps blood parameters within the biological range (Gross et al. 2011) [16],. This test can be used to check the nutritional and metabolic status of livestock individually or in groups. Metabolic profile testing also has great benefits for the early identification of energy metabolism disorders in cattle (Prodanovic et al. 2012). [18], Research results on blood metabolites (Blood Urea Nitrogen / BUN, β -hydroxybutyric acid / BHBA, Non-esterified fatty acids / NEFA) presented in Table .1

Table 1. Mean Blood Metabolite Concentrations at 60 and 150 Days of Pregnancy.

Variables	Mean	
	PGF2 α	PGF2 α + GnRH
<i>β-hydroxy butirate acid (BHBA) mg/dl</i>		
When in heat	12.48 $\pm$ 1.19 ^c	12,48 $\pm$ 1,64 ^d
Pregnancy 60 days	12.11 $\pm$ 1.35 ^c	12.57 $\pm$ 2.50 ^d
Pregnancy 150 days	11.35 $\pm$ 1.30 ^c	10.93 $\pm$ 1.28 ^d
<i>Non Esterified Fatty Acids (NEFA) mmol/l</i>		
When in heat	2.27 $\pm$ 0.49 ^c	2.32 $\pm$ 0.50 ^d
Pregnancy 60 days	1.95 $\pm$ 0.27 ^c	1.75 $\pm$ 0.23 ^d
Pregnancy 150 days	1.85 $\pm$ 0.13 ^c	1.84 $\pm$ 0.24 ^d
<i>Blood Urea Nitrogen (BUN). mg / dl</i>		
When in heat	30.16 $\pm$ 5.30 ^c	27.20 $\pm$ 2.77 ^d
Pregnancy 60 days	24.31 $\pm$ 3.03 ^c	23.10 $\pm$ 1.77 ^d
Pregnancy 150 days	22.57 $\pm$ 2.31 ^c	22.75 $\pm$ 2.29 ^d

a,b,c, d Mean for each variable on the same line with different superscripts showing significant differences (P. <0.05)

Based on the results in Table 1., it turns out that the average blood urea nitrogen (BUN) concentration of Pasundan cattle when estrus, 60 and 150 days pregnant, synchronized with estrus (PGF2 α + PGF2 α) and ovulation synchronization (PGF2 α + GnRH + PGF2 α) are still in the normal range. The range of BUN concentrations in normal cattle is 6-27 mg/dl (Meyer and Harvey (2004).[28], The concentrations of non-esterification fatty acid (NEFA) and beta-hydroxybutyrate (BHBA) are higher than normal. The normal range of beta hydroxy butyric acid (BHBA) is <9.00 mg dL-1 (Julie et al., 2013) [29], and the normal range of NEFA is 1.00 - 2.00 mmol L-1 (Julie et al., 2013) [29] This condition is thought to be due to a lack of feed consumed by cows, including quality and quantity. Forage provided only in the form of field grass around rubber plantations and dry straw, resulting in a negative energy balance (NEB). Increased concentrations of BHBA and NEFA indicate an indication of the mobilization of carbohydrates, proteins, lipids, and fatty acid oxidation in producing energy, on the other hand. high concentrations of BHBA lead to an increased risk of disease after

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childbirth (Shaka et al., 2006). [30], When cattle experience Negative Energy Balance (NEB), most of them are When glucose will be used for reproduction, the body will lack energy, then the fat reserves in the body will be used as a source of energy (Reist et al., 2000) [31],. Blood glucose is a sugar contained in the blood which is formed from carbohydrates in feed and stored as glycogen in the liver and muscles. Forage is the main source of energy consisting of starch, sugar, cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin, and pectin, which are precursors of fat and lactose. (Franca et al [32],

The results of the analysis of variance showed that estrous synchronization (PGF2 α -PGF2 α) and ovulation synchronization (PGF2 α -GnRH- PGF2 α) had no significant effect (P> 0.05) on the concentrations of NEFA, BHBA, and BUN. This condition is suspected that the feed intake factor affects the reproductive performance of Pasundan cattle. The relationship between reproduction and nutritional status is closely related, namely nutritional deficiencies as the main factor inhibiting the reproductive system of cattle in tropical areas (Wetterman et al., 2003). [33], Lack of nutrition or insufficient feed input can have a direct effect on reproductive efficiency such as low reproductive performance and productivity (Salem et al., 2006) [34],. The main obstacle to developing Pasundan cattle in plantation areas (rubber and teak) is the low nutritional content of natural grasses and the amount of grass production is still far from sufficient, especially during the dry season (Hilmia, 2013) [35]. Cows with high non-esterified fatty acids (NEFA) will mobilize more fat reserves to support broodstock productivity which results in a drastic decrease in body weight and cow's BCS to compensate for NEFA (Grunwalduced et al., 2005) [36],.

Reproductive Performance (Estrus Intensity, Service Perception, Conception Rate).

The results showed that the estrus intensity, service preconception, and conception rate of Pasundan cattle are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Service Perception Profile, Conception Rate, and Blood Metabolites (BHBA, NEFA, and BUN).

Variables	Mean	
Reproductive Performance	PGF2 α	PGF2 α + GnRH
Estrous intensity (%)		
Score 1 (+) (%)	20	10
Score 2 (++) (%)	50	70
Score 3 (+++) (%)	30	20
Service Perconception (time)	1.3	1.1
Conception Rate (%)	70	80
<i>β-hydroxy butirate acid (BHBA) mg/dl</i>	11.75 $\pm$ 1.32	11.73 $\pm$ 1.78
<i>Non Esterified Fatty Acids (NEFA) mmol/l</i>	1.90 $\pm$ 0.20	1.8 $\pm$ 0.24
<i>Blood Urea Nitrogen (BUN). mg / dl</i>	23.44 $\pm$ 2.60	22.92 $\pm$ 1.53

Based on the results in Table 2, shows that the oestrus intensity of Pasundan cattle that is synchronized with ovulation (PGF2 α + GnRH + PGF2 α) is better than that of estrus synchronized (PGF2 α + PGF2 α). The difference in estrous intensity is thought to be due to the different factors of individual cows in response to

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exogenous hormone induction as a result of differences in the ability of maximum secretion of lust hormones for each individual. Differences in heat intensity between one cow and another can be caused by non-treatment factors such as livestock conditions, individual factors, work activities carried out, and livestock interactions (Kune and Najamudin (2002) [7],. Cervical mucus is produced by secretory cells that are found in the endocervix, the quality and quantity of cervical mucus are strongly influenced by the condition of hormones secreted during lust (Tsiliganni et al., 2011). Hormonal circulation in the body greatly affects the process of follicular growth, ovulation, and the formation of the corpus luteum (Hafizuddin et al., 2012) [4], Administration of exogenous GnRH will lead to the synergy of FSH and LH release from the pituitary, resulting in faster development of dominant follicles, leading to accelerated development of ovulatory follicles (Hasan et al., 2016) [37],. estrus, then the identification of estrus will be more accurate and the implementation of IB will be more accurate the more correct.

The results in Table 2. indicate that there is a correlation between the intensity of lust with service pre-conception (S / C). The S / C value describes the fertility level of female cows, the lower the value, the higher the fertility of the female cows in IB and vice versa, the higher the S / C value, the lower the fertility rate of the female cows in the group. The mean service pre-conception (S / C) and conception rate (CR) of ovulation-synchronized Pasundan cattle (PGF2 α + GnRH + PGF2 α) were higher than those synchronized estrus (PGF2 α + PGF2 α) with S / C and CR values 1.1 times and respectively. 80% VS 1.3 times and 70%. This condition indicates that the use of GnRH can uniform ovulation in Pasundan heifers, thereby increasing reproductive performance. The GnRH hormone functions to stimulate the hypofunction of LH and FSH which work together to stimulate follicles and corpus luteum formation. the influence of the hormone GnRH to stimulate follicular growth and the formation of the corpus luteum after ovulation (Putro, 2008) [38]. The increase and decrease in progesterone levels are in line with the development of the corpus luteum (Arimbawa et al., 2012) [39].

The Relationship Between Reproductive Performance and Blood Metabolite Concentrations

The mean blood metabolite levels of both BHBA, NEFA, and BUN at estrus and at 60 days and 150 days of pregnancy, the estrus synchronization (PGF2 α + PGF2 α) was relatively higher than ovulation synchronization (PGF2 α + GnRH + PGF2 α), namely BHBA (11.75 mg respectively) / dl vs 11.73 mg/dl), NEFA (1.9 mmol / l vs 1.8 mmol / l), BUN (23.44 mg/dl vs 22.92 mg/dl). Based on the results of the analysis of variance, the results were not significantly different ($P > 0.05$) between treatments on the concentration of BHBA; NEFA; BUN during estrus, 60 and 150 days pregnant. Significant variation of blood metabolite composition between species, race, sex, or breed (Stojevic et al. 2008[40]; Balicki et al. 2007[41],), age (Addas et al., 2012[42],) (Balicki et al. 2007[41],), reproductive status, stress, transportation (Balicki et al. 2007[41],) and also influenced by other factors such as animal origin, management, geography, animal development stage (Ali 2008) [43], and climate (Ali, 2008 [43], and Lager and Jordan 2012) [44],.

The success of fertilization until pregnancy and an increase in estrous quality is related to the value of BCS (Wahyudi, 2008[45],). If livestock lack energy because energy intake is not sufficient, then energy reserves in the form of fat will be broken down into NEFA and glycerol which can be used as a source of energy for cows to give birth (Tasse, 2014). [17], Blood NEFA is an indicator to assess the energy status of livestock, but blood NEFA concentration can be affected by stress. Increasing the concentration of NEFA can lead to early embryo death, resulting in poor reproductive performance, namely a low percentage of pregnancy. Lack of nutrients or insufficient feed input can have a direct effect on reproductive efficiency (Suryahadi 2004) [46],. Low glucose levels can cause high levels of nonesterified fatty acids (NEFA) which have toxic effects on follicles, oocytes, embryos, and fetuses, and decrease GnRH secretion by the hypothalamus (Adewuyi et al., 2005) [21],. The decrease in GnRH will inhibit the synthesis of FSH and LH in the anterior and pituitary causing the follicle to not develop and not appear in heat (Oguike and Okocha, 2008) [47],. Low concentrations of blood glucose and total protein lead to impaired reproductive hormone function and not optimal reproductive tract function, leading to failure of the follicle, oocyte, and embryo development which will lead to early embryo death and

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failure of fertilization which results in repeated mating (Khan et al., 2010) [48], Glucose deficiency can also inhibit the synthesis of follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) and luteinizing hormone (LH) which results in inhibition of the development of follicles, ova, estrogen, and progesterone (Prihatno, 2007). [49], Feed as a factor that causes reproductive disorders and infertility is often compound, meaning that a deficiency of a substance in the feed ration is followed by a deficiency in other feed substances (Annashru, 2017) [50],. Low blood glucose levels in cattle can cause high concentrations of non-esterified fatty acids (NEFA).) which has a toxic effect on follicles, oocytes, embryos, and fetuses (Caldieramory et al., 2007[51],), also indicates low energy (carbohydrates) in the ration (Prihatno et al., 2013). High BUN concentrations will suppress the immune system, low BUN will affect the pituitary-pituitary-ovarian axis, have a toxic effect on sperm, eggs, and embryos, and result in decreased fertility (National Research Council, 2001[22],; Roy et al. 2011[23],; and Bindari et al., 2013[24],. Variations in serum BUN concentrations are influenced by diet, race, muscle mass, and sex (Hammond, 2006) [52],; The relationship between reproductive performance (Service Per Conception, Conception rate) and the concentration of blood metabolites (BHBA, NEFA, BUN) is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Relationship Between Reproductive Performance (Service Per Conception, Conception rate) and Blood Metabolite Concentration (BHBA, NEFA, BUN)

Reproductive Performance	Mean	Correlation Coefficient
Service Perconception (Time)	1.2	-
BHBA (mg dl ⁻¹)	10.25±1.54*	0.027*
NEFA (mmol L ⁻¹)	1.76 ± 0.37*	0.317*
BUN (mg dL ⁻¹)	22.70± 2.70**	0.014*
Conception rate (%)	75.0	
BHBA (mg dl ⁻¹)	12.33±1.81*	3.277*
NEFA (mmol L ⁻¹)	1.85±0.25**	56.988**
BUN (mg dL ⁻¹)	23.70 ±2.40*	2.553*

Superscript* menunjukkan tingkat korelasi nyata (P<0.05) dan ** sangat nyata (P<0.01) dengan service preconception dan conception rate

Table 4. Correlation Regression Equations

Reproduction Performance	Correlation Regression Equation	R ²
Service Perconception Blood Metabolites (BHBA,NEFA,BUN))	S /C =2.973 -0.027X1-0.317X2-0.014X3	0.2538
Conception rate Blood Metabolite (BHBA, NEFA, BUN))	CR =108.491 -3.277X1-56.988X2-2.553X3	0.5082

Based on the regression equation, it turns out that BHBA, BUN, and NEFA all have negative regression coefficients, meaning that it will reduce the Service preconception and conception rate if a negative nutrient balance occurs. Lack of nutrient substrates will cause the mobilization of food reserves such as fat (triglycerides) which are accumulated during pregnancy and will cause the accumulation of acetyl CoA and cannot enter the citric acid cycle, so it will be converted into ketones such as acetone, β-OH butyrate as a result of 2 mol condensation. acetyl CoA. Likewise, if protein metabolism occurs, the livestock is in a negative nitrogen balance which is indicated by an increase in blood urea nitrogen concentration. The same thing in the products of triglyceride fat metabolism will be converted into non-esterificated fatty acid (NEFA) free fatty acids (Pradhan et al., 2008). [53],

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Based on the results of the correlation analysis (in Table 3), it shows that service per conception has a significant relationship ($P < 0.005$) with BHBA (-0.027), NEFA (-0.317), and BUN (-0.014). These results indicate that service per conception has an inversely related relationship with the concentration of blood metabolites (BHBA, NEFA, BUN). This means that the value of service per conception will be higher (the value is low) if the concentration of blood metabolites increases due to poor nutritional intake before artificial insemination and during pregnancy. This is because the metabolite concentration increases if there is a negative nutrient balance intake, resulting in a catabolic process or a change in food reserves from the body. The results of the regression analysis show that according to the regression equation $S / C = -0.027X_3 - 0.317X_4 + 0.014X_5$ with a determination coefficient of 0.2538 means that service per conception is influenced by the concentration of blood metabolites by 25.38%.

The results showed that the conception rate had a very significant negative relationship ($P < 0.001$) with NEFA (-56.988), and a significant relationship ($P < 0.05$) with BHBA (-3.277) and BUN (-2.553). showed that the conception rate was inversely related to the concentration of blood metabolites (NEFA, BHBA, and BUN) during pregnancy. This means that the conception rate will be lower if the concentration of blood metabolites increases due to poor nutritional intake during pregnancy. Metabolite concentrations increase if there is a negative nutrient balance intake, resulting in a catabolic process or a change in food reserves from the body due to lack of energy (especially carbohydrates) feed. The results of the regression analysis show that according to the regression equation $CR = 108,491 - 3,277X_1 - 56.988X_2 - 2.553X_3$ with a determination coefficient of 0.5082 which means that service per conception is influenced by the concentration of blood metabolites by 50.82%.

CONCLUSION

The concentration of β -hydroxybutyric acid (BHBA), blood urea nitrogen (BUN), and non-esterified fatty acid (NEFA) has a strong relationship (coefficient of determination $> 50\%$) and is inversely related to the conception rate, but has a weak relationship (coefficient determination $< 50\%$) and inversely proportional to service preconception.

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